

REDUCTION OF CURING INDUCED FIBER STRESSES BY CURE CYCLE OPTIMIZATION IN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The matrix volume changes associated with thermal expansion/contraction and cure shrinkage produce significant stresses on fiber during the standard curing cycle of polymer matrix composites. Experimental results on single fiber graphite fiber/epoxy composites show that the fiber is subjected to significant tensile stresses during the standard curing cycle. Two stress producing mechanisms have been identified. These mechanisms are - matrix thermal expansion/contraction and matrix cure shrinkage. A method is developed to modify the curing cycle in a manner such that the matrix volume change due to temperature increase is simultaneously cancelled by matrix curing shrinkage. This modified curing cycle has been shown to significantly reduce the curing induced fiber tensile stresses for gr/ep composites.

INTRODUCTION

Several studies have been conducted to understand the cure kinetics of thermoset resins [1,2]. One of the main objectives of these studies has been to understand how the chemical and thermal changes encountered during curing of these resins lead to the residual stresses in composites [3,4]. The effect of residual stresses generated during curing is reflected in the mechanical properties of cured composites [5]. In calculating the thermal residual stress in composites, a stress-free state at the highest temperature in the curing cycle is commonly assumed. Thus the attention is focused on the optimization of the cooling path so as to minimize the residual stresses in composites.

In the case of thermoset matrices, significant matrix volume changes occur during its curing cycle. These matrices undergo expansion as well as shrinkage during its curing cycle [2,6]. The expansion is associated with the increase in the volume of epoxy when temperature is increased. The contraction is associated with the reduction in free volume during the polymer crosslinking. These matrix volume changes may produce significant stresses in fiber at various stages of the curing cycle.

Our objective in this research has been to monitor the fiber stresses and identify the responsible mechanisms during a typical two-stage thermoset epoxy matrix curing cycle in various single fiber/epoxy composites. This paper presents a specific experimental technique for evaluating these residual stresses. Our results on graphite fibers and amine cured epoxy systems suggest that there are primarily two mechanisms which produce stresses in the fiber. These mechanisms are volume change due to temperature, and the cure shrinkage. We present results to show the significance of each of these mechanisms at different stages of the curing cycle. We also present a method to modify the curing cycle in a manner such that the matrix volume change due to temperature increase is simultaneously cancelled by matrix curing shrinkage. The modified curing cycle has been shown to significantly reduce the curing induced fiber tensile stresses for gr/ep composites.

MATERIAL

The residual stress measurements were made for AS-4 graphite fibers embedded in epoxy matrix. The matrix is a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (EPON 828, Shell Chemical Company) cured with 14.5 parts per hundred by weight of meta-phenylene diamine (mPDA, Aldrich Chemical Company). The matrix was mixed, debulked under vacuum for 10 minutes and subjected to two-step cure cycle in air. In the first cycle the temperature of the material was increased from room temperature to 75°C (167°F) and is held constant for two hours. The temperature was then increased to a second dwell temperature at 125°C (257°F) and held constant for two hours. After the second dwell, the heating cycle was stopped and the specimen was allowed to cool down to room temperature. The purpose of the first dwell is to allow gases and other volatiles to escape from the matrix material and to allow the matrix to flow. The purpose of the second dwell time is to allow crosslinking of the polymer to take place. The matrix cured in this manner has the modulus of 3.6 GPa and tensile strength of 89.6 MPa.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The procedure involves applying a known tension to a fiber having fixed ends, and then monitoring the change in the fiber tension when the matrix around the fiber is subjected to a given temperature-time curing cycle. One end of the fiber is fixed to a rigid support. The other end of the fiber is passed through a cavity in a silicone mold and glued to a load cell. The thickness of the base of the silicone mold was kept as small as possible (about 0.5 mm) to minimize the effect of silicone volume change on experimental results.

A predetermined tension is applied to the fiber. The resin is heated to 75°C, mixed with the hardener and the mixture degassed for about 10 minutes in a vacuum oven and then the resin-hardener mixture is poured around the fiber in the cavity of the silicone mold. The specimen is then subjected to a two-step cure cycle. The heat is applied to the resin by a strip-heater. The temperature is controlled by means of a power distributor and a temperature controller. A ceramic plate is placed between the heated zone and the load cell to prevent heating of the load cell. The temperature is monitored by means of a thermocouple placed directly above the specimen. The output from the load cell and the thermocouple is recorded during the entire curing process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A representative profile of fiber tension change during the curing of a single graphite fiber/epoxy composite is shown in Fig. 1. The fiber tension is unchanged for the first one and half hours at 75°C. Some increase in fiber tension occurs during the last half hour at 75°C. The fiber tension drops rapidly when the temperature is increased from the first dwell period (75°C) to the second dwell period (125°C). Subsequent to the tension drop to a minimum value, there is again a slow increase in the fiber tension during the first half hour at 125°C. No tension change is observed during the last one and a half hours at 125°C. During the cooling path, the fiber tension again increases and stabilizes at the completion of cooling.

Figure 1. Change in fiber tension measured at the load cell during the curing cycle of a single fiber gr/ep composite.

Fig. 2 illustrates the mechanisms believed to be responsible for producing the changes in the fiber tension during the curing cycle. This figure shows only the effects of matrix volume change on the fiber tension curves. There are two mechanisms that produce matrix volume change. These are - thermal expansion/contraction (solid arrows) and matrix crosslinking (hollow arrows). In the region AB, matrix volume increases due to thermal expansion. However, sufficient fiber/matrix interface shear strength has not yet developed because of insufficient matrix crosslinking in this

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the mechanisms responsible for producing stress in the fiber when a thermoset matrix surrounding the fiber is subjected to the curing cycle.

region. Therefore, when the matrix volume increases, the matrix simply flows over the fiber without affecting the fiber tension. The change in fiber tension during the region BC suggests that the matrix polymerization has already begun towards the later part of the first dwell period. There is volume shrinkage associated with matrix polymerization [6]. The curing shrinkage is caused by the reaction and rearrangement of the molecules into a more compact configuration. Since the matrix has partially polymerized, the fiber/matrix interface can now respond to matrix volume changes. Therefore, the effect of matrix cure shrinkage is reflected in the fiber tension increase in region BC. In region CD, when temperature is increased to 125°C, the two mechanisms operate simultaneously. However, because of the rapid heating rate the matrix thermal expansion dominates the cure shrinkage resulting in net increase in matrix volume. Therefore, the fiber tension measured at the load cell decreases in region CD. In region DE, the matrix thermal expansion stops but crosslinking process continues. The effect of crosslinking shrinkage is again reflected in the increase in fiber tension in region DE. The matrix crosslinking is believed to be complete at point E, and therefore, neither of the two mechanisms operate in region EF. Finally in region FG, when the cooling starts, there is matrix volume reduction associated only with a temperature decrease. The matrix volume reduction again causes an increase in the fiber tension.

The average fiber stress in these composites during the curing cycle is calculated from simple mechanistic analysis. Assuming a uniform fiber stress distribution along the embedded fiber length, the curing induced fiber stress at any time 't' (Fig. 3) can be related to the fiber tension T(t) at the load cell as follows:

$$\sigma_f(t) = -2 \frac{T(t) - T(0)}{A_f} \left(\frac{L_1}{L_2} \right) - \alpha_f (\Delta T) E_f \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

where, α_f is the coefficient of thermal expansion of the fiber along the fiber axis and ΔT is the

Figure 3. Fiber stress (σ_f) produced by matrix volume change during the matrix curing cycle.

temperature increase resulting from applied temperature and from the exothermic reactions during the crosslinking [7]. However, since the coefficient of thermal expansion (α_f) of fiber is quite small (α_f for graphite fiber = -1.6 to -0.9 (10^{-6})/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$), the contribution of the second term in comparison to the first term in Eq. (1) to the fiber stress is insignificant. Therefore, the average fiber stress is approximated as:

$$\sigma_f(t) = -2 \frac{T(t) - T(0)}{A_f} \left(\frac{L_1}{L_2} \right) \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

Note that Eq. (2) does not include the stresses resulting from the fiber pre-tension $T(0)$.

The fiber stresses calculated from Eq. (2) for a single fiber gr/ep composite are plotted in Fig. 4. The fiber stresses shown in Fig. 4 are due only to the matrix volume change, i.e., the fiber stresses resulting from the fiber pre-tension are not included. An important observation in Fig. 4 is that when the temperature is raised from the first dwell to the second dwell periods the embedded fiber experiences a tensile stress peak (≈ 1.2 GPa). The mechanisms responsible for the tensile stress peak are shown in Fig. 2 (region CD).

Independent tensile tests on graphite fiber samples revealed that fiber strength ranged from 2.5 to 3 GPa. Therefore, if these fibers are pre-tensioned to an initial stress of about 1.3 to 1.8

Figure 4. Curing induced fiber stresses that occur during the commonly used curing cycle for a gr/ep composite.

GPa, the combined tensile stress (curing induced stress plus the initial stress) in the embedded fiber should reach the fiber failure stress, i.e., in those samples a fiber fracture may occur during the curing cycle. To verify this, tests were conducted on single fiber gr/ep specimens in which the fiber prestress was about 1.3 of the expected fiber failure load. Results on two of those specimens having pre-tensions of 6.5 g (1.3 GPa) and 7.0 g (1.4 GPa) are shown in Fig. 5. No fiber crack was detected in the 6.5 g fiber pre-tensioned specimen. However, in the 7.0 g fiber pre-tensioned specimen, one fiber crack was detected. The fiber cracks were observed in several other specimens in which the fiber tension was larger than 7.0 g (1.4 GPa). These observations suggest that although the analysis that is used to calculate the fiber stress during the curing is based on some gross assumptions (such as uniform fiber stress along the entire embedded length), it still agrees quite well with the experimental observations.

Figure 5. a) The specimen cured with 6.5 g (1.3 GPa) fiber pretension did not show any fiber breaks; b) The specimen cured with 7.0 g (1.5 GPa) fiber pretension showed fiber breaks; c) photograph of a fiber break detected in specimen (b).

To verify that the fiber fracture occurs within a short time interval when the temperature is raised 75°C to 125°C, two additional experiments were conducted. In both of these specimens, the fiber was pre-tensioned to about 70% of their expected failure load. In one of the specimens the test was terminated at point A in the temperature-time curve (see Fig. 6a). The specimen was removed and immediately examined under an optical microscope. No fiber crack was detected in this specimen. The other specimen was removed at point B in the temperature-time cycle and immediately examined under the microscope. This specimen did show fiber cracks (see Fig. 6b).

Figure 6. a) Schematic of curing cycle showing points A and B where the specimens were removed for examination under a microscope; b) photograph of a fiber break detected in a specimen removed at point B. No fiber break occurred in specimen removed at point A.

One of the applications of such experiments may be in the optimization of the curing cycle to obtain the desired fiber residual stresses in the cured composite. For example, when the stresses resulting from the fiber pre-tension are superimposed on the curing induced fiber stresses shown in Fig. 4, the entire fiber stress curve will move up (see Fig. 7). Thus the fiber compressive stresses at the

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the procedure to minimize the curing induced fiber tensile stress. Solid arrows (\Rightarrow) represent matrix volume change due to heat; hollow arrows (\Rightarrow) represent matrix crosslinking shrinkage: a) With the conventional curing cycle, the matrix volume increase due to thermal expansion can not be completely cancelled by its cure shrinkage, i.e., the solid arrows are larger than the hollow arrows; b) In the optimized cycle the rate of matrix thermal expansion is decreased to a level where it can be cancelled by the cure shrinkage, i.e., solid arrows are similar to hollow arrows.

end of the cooling cycle can be reduced by applying a tensile load to the fibers in a composite prior to subjecting them to the curing cycle. However, the tensile stresses that occur during the transition from the first dwell to the second dwell period will also increase. These tensile stresses can cause the tensile fracture of the fiber during the curing. According to the mechanisms shown in Fig. 2, there are two sources that contribute to the fiber stress during the transition period (region CD in Fig. 2). These two mechanisms oppose each other. Independent tests have shown that the matrix total volume change due to temperature increase is of about the same order of magnitude as that due to cure shrinkage. Therefore, it should be possible to change the curing cycle in a manner such that matrix thermal expansion can be simultaneously cancelled by the cure shrinkage. Fig. 7 shows the schematic representation of such an approach.

To test the validity of such an approach, the heating rate for the transition period (i.e., from 75°C to 125°C) was arbitrarily decreased from about 5°/min (traditional curing cycle, Fig. 4) to 0.14°/min. The curing induced fiber stresses recorded during the curing cycle corresponding to a rate of 0.14°/min are shown in Fig. 8. Comparison of Fig. 4 and 8 shows that the reduced heating rate almost completely eliminates the fiber tensile stress. The measurements of glass transition temperature on the specimens cured using these two curing cycles showed little difference. A model has also been developed to predict the heating rate that will minimize the curing induced

Figure 8. Reduction of curing induced fiber stresses in a graphite/ epoxy composite by curing cycle modification.

fiber stresses for a given fiber-matrix system. The work on the application of this model is currently in progress. This procedure can also be used to provide information about when the heating cycle should be stopped. According to the results shown in Fig. 4 and 8, it can be seen that after point C in the curing cycle there is no significant change in fiber stress. This suggests that matrix volume is not changing beyond point C, i.e., the matrix curing may be about complete at this point. Thus the cooldown can be started at point C. This issue is currently being investigated. Additional research is also being conducted to study the effect of cure cycle modification on mechanical and physical properties of the polymer, fiber-matrix interface, and glass transition temperature, etc.

CONCLUSIONS

A simple experimental method has been developed to determine the curing induced fiber stresses and then use this information to modify the curing cycle and minimizes these fiber stresses in polymer matrix composites. Two mechanisms that produce these fiber stresses have been identified. These are: the thermal expansion and contraction of matrix due to temperature change and the matrix cure shrinkage. The relative contributions of each of these two mechanisms to fiber stresses in different regions of the curing cycle are determined. The simple mechanistic analysis used to calculate the fiber stress agrees well with the experimental results. The results on single fiber gr/ep composites show that significant tensile stresses are produced during the curing cycle. The regions in the temperature-time curing cycle where the fiber stresses occur are identified. It has been demonstrated that by modifying the curing cycle in a way such that matrix thermal expansion is simultaneously cancelled by matrix crosslinking shrinkage, the curing induced fiber stresses can be almost completely eliminated for gr/ep composites.

The procedure presented here can be useful in addressing the following issues:

1. It can be used to determine the curing cycle to minimize the curing induced fiber stresses.
2. It can be used to determine the time for the completion of a curing cycle.

3. During the manufacture of composites, fiber waviness occurs from the nonuniform cooling of a composite laminate. One of the methods to prevent the fiber waviness is to pretension the fibers. However, Fig. 1 shows that with a traditional curing cycle the curing induced fiber tensile stresses are significant and they may cause tensile fracture of fibers if fiber pretension is high. With the optimized cycle, the curing induced fiber tensile stresses are minimized, and therefore, fiber pretensioning method can be used with the optimized cycle.
4. Fiber pretensioning method (together with the optimized curing cycle) can be used to obtain a desired state of fiber residual stress in a cured composite.

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